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ROLE OF *RASAYANA* AND *VAJIKARANA* IN THE MANAGEMENT OF INFERTILITY – A REVIEW STUDY

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Abstract

Infertility is major cause of concern in people of reproductive age. Prevalence of Infertility is increasing at alarming rate. WHO estimates one in six people have experienced infertility. In general, around 15-20% couple of reproductive age suffer from infertility worldwide. In India, Prevalence is around 23%. It varies from state to state. Many factors contribute to it like poor lifestyle choices, environmental pollution, exposure to various radiations and more stressful life. Psychological factor also plays very important role. *Ayurveda* promotes health by preventive as well as curative aspect along with improving healing capacity. *Rasayana* and *Vajikarana*, one among the *Ashtangas* of *Ayurveda* focus on holistic approach in improving overall health and quality of life of individual. *Rasayana* balances the *Doshas* and slows down degenerative changes improving neuro endocrine immune system. *Vajikarana* not only improves reproductive system but also relieves stress and mental problems.

Key Words:

Rasayana, Vajikarana, Infertility.

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INTRODUCTION:

Every living being has been blessed by god to reproduce itself and lengthen their legacy. Pregnancy and child-bearing capability is noblest gift given only to women. Motherhood is greatest milestone in the life of woman. But nowadays due to fast-track life, enormous work, family pressure and disturbed work-life balance, many lifestyle disorders are on rise. Infertility is one of the most burning concern in the people of reproductive age. Infertility is when person is unable to produce progeny even after having regular, unprotected, planned intercourse. Infertility can be primary meaning couple or person never has pregnancy before and secondary meaning there was successful pregnancy previously but unable to produce progeny now. Though modern science has discovered many of its etiological factors and provided measures for its management, still the success rate is below par.

On the other hand, *Ayurveda* has described infertility as *Vandhyatva* and has provided fundamental principles and measures to combat it. There is all praise for person with children and one without children is considered as tree without flowers and fruits.¹ It is also considered as a means for attainment of *Purusharthas* (goals of a human life), *Dharma* (moral values, righteousness), *Artha* (prosperity, economic values), *Kama* (pleasure, love, psychological values) and *Moksha* (liberation, spiritual values).² Therefore, having a child is an act which enhances *Yasha* (success in life), *Dharma* (righteousness), *Maana* (self-respect), *Srikulavardhana* (prosperity and lineage), ultimately aiming a *Supraja* (healthy progeny) advocating the principles of eugenics.³

Infertility is of dire concern as it affects approximately 13-16% couples worldwide. It is believed that 60-80 million couple suffer from infertility every year out of which 15-20 million couple belong to Indian origin. According to WHO the prevalence of the same in India is between 3.9% and 16.8% which is increasing in an alarming rate. The incidences increase due to the diversified daily routine and adapting modernization which affect the physiological factors causes irregular menstruation, ovulation disorders, polycystic ovary syndrome, fallopian tube blockage, endometriosis, hormonal disorders and uterine abnormalities, etc. The adverse effect of changing environment and pollution also induces cases of depression, stress and obesity which have adverse effect on fertility.^{4 5 6 7}

There are four important factors known as *Garbha Sambhava Samagri* that is *Rutu*, *Kshetra*, *Ambu* and *Beeja*. Normal function of all these ensure safe and healthy pregnancy. *Kshetra* denotes healthy female genital track which will facilitate entry of sperm, *Ambu* represent nutritional elements and hormones and *Beeja* denotes Ovum.⁸ *Ayurveda* not only focuses on curing the disease but also on improving health. *Rasayana* and *Vajikarana* is one of the prime branch of *Ashtangas* of *Ayurveda* which promotes health by retarding ageing process. *Vajikarana* improves function of reproductive organs and nourishes *Saptadhatus*.

Aim:

To explore the role of *Rasayana* and *Vajikarana* in Infertility.

Objectives:

To evaluate promotive and preventive effect of *Rasayana* and *Vajikarana* in Infertility.

Materials and Methods:

To carry out this review study, classical Ayurvedic texts like *Ashtanga Hridayam*, *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, etc. along with scientific research articles, and the electronic databases or search engines like Pubmed, google scholar were explored.

Name of database	Search terms	Number of articles
Pub med central	<i>Rasayana</i> and Infertility	6
	<i>Vajikarana</i> and Infertility	5
Google Scholar	<i>Rasayana</i> and <i>Vajikarana</i> in Infertility	340
Ayush research portal	<i>Rasayana</i> and <i>Vajikarana</i> in Infertility	02

Review of literature:

Vandhyatva or Infertility is the major leading concern which not only affect physical but also mental health of couple. The word “*Vandhya*” is derived from the root of “*vandha*” with “*yak*” suffix which means barren, unproductive, fruitless and useless. The woman in whom there is hindrance of any kind to the normal process of conception is *Vandhya*. *Ayurveda* has emphasized importance of holistic approach i.e. healthy ovum, healthy sperm and healthy uterus. Be it male or female, reproductive health depends on the health of *Shukradhatu*. Excessive consumption of unwholesome diet, habitual use of *Ruksha*, *Ushna*, *Katu*, *Kashaya* rich food articles. Excessive sexual indulgence, untimely sexual practices and *Vegavidharana* are also responsible for infertility. *Acharya Kashyapa* has mentioned *Pushpaghni* under *Revati Jatharini* in which woman’s menstruation is regular but still unable to conceive. *Acharyas* have mentioned that *Artavavaha Dushti* causes *Abhijata* i.e. it is unable for *Prajotpadana*. *Acharya Charaka* has especially mentioned diseases of *Yoni* in separate *Adhyaya*.

Acharana, *Aticharana*, *Putraghni*, etc *Yonivyapadas* make women unable to conceive.

According to different *acharyaas*

<i>Charaka</i>	<i>Ashtanga</i>	<i>Bhela</i>	<i>Kashyapa</i>
1) <i>Vandhya</i> (absence of ovum) 2) <i>Apraja</i> (Primary infertility) 3) <i>Supraja</i> (Secondary infertility)	<i>Yonivyapada</i> (disorders of uterus) and <i>Putraghni</i> (demise of first child) and <i>Jataghni</i> (stillbirth)	<i>Vandhyatva</i> occurs due to <i>Beeja Dushti</i> (abnormalities in ovum and sperm), <i>Vegavrodha</i> (suppression of urges) and <i>Yonivyapada</i> (disorders of reproductive system)	<i>Vandhyatva</i> as disorder of <i>Vata</i> . Also explained in <i>Jatharinis</i> .

Samprapti

Articles critically reviewed:

1. Role of *Ayurveda* in the management of *Vandhyatva* w.s.r. to Infertility (<https://www.jaims.in/jaims/article/view/1061/1085>)
2. The critical aspects of Infertility in *Ayurveda* (<https://www.sjsach.org.in/wpcontent/uploads/2015/01/Ayursurabhi-Jul-Aug-2014.pdf>)
3. An *Ayurvedic* literature review on *Stree Vandhyatva*. (https://wjpr.s3.ap-south-1.amazonaws.com/article_issue/690a8b4522d992b8540588b14ee10546.pdf)
4. An *Ayurvedic* literature review on *Shukradushti*. (https://wjpr.s3.ap-south-1.amazonaws.com/article_issue/5b577b36f8ebab40576200df7e33c1bf.pdf)
5. Role of *Rasayana* and *Vajikarana* in the management of Infertility with examples of case study (<https://www.ijfmr.com/>)
6. An insight into ayurvedic aspects of male reproductive health with special reference to preconception care (<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/51d5/005bbf204ed239cb25a48c3eee6822e-f79e7.pdf>)

Result and Discussion:

Infertility treatment mostly focuses on treating couples on the basis of frequency of intercourse during the fertile window, management of any dysfunction, treating any pelvic or tubal diseases. Treatment is done according to causative factor. Intrauterine insemination with either clomiphene citrate or gonadotropin therapy, IVF are some of the treatments done in infertility. But *Rasayana* and *Vajikarana* improves health by strengthening body's own healing system and balancing *Dhatus*. *Rasayana* improves body's nutrition. It gives *Pushti* to all seven *Dhatus* to all ages from paediatrics to geriatrics.⁹ It rejuvenates body by holistic health promoting approach. *Acharya Rasayana* i.e. proper conduct and behaviour also modulates the neuro endocrine system as stated by *Acharya Charaka – Labhopayo hi Shastanam Rasadinam Rasayanam*.¹⁰ *Vajikarana* being specialized therapy for reproductive health and enhancing sexual function have high rate of curing infertility. It has been proved to be 90% effective. *Vajikarana* also acts on higher centre of the Brain i.e. the hypothalamus and limbic System. It deals with strengthening and improving sexual competency and conception of healthy offsprings along with curing disturbed spermatogenesis, defects in semen or any reproduction related problems. It improves the physical, psychological and social health which imparts great impression in reproductive health.

Vata, *Pitta* and *Kapha* maintains body and mind. *Rasayana* and *Vajikarana* balance this *Tridoshas*. *Agni* regulates proper digestion of food, metabolic products and converts food into essential energy form required for vital activity of bodily functions. *Rasayana* and *Vajikarana* improve *Agni*, thus keeping bodily functions stable.

CHIKITSA

Shukra Dusti^{11 12 13}	Specific Treatment
<i>Vataja</i>	<i>Niruha, Anuvasana¹⁴</i>
<i>Pittaja</i>	<i>Abhaya Amalakki rasayana</i>
<i>Kaphaja</i>	<i>Pippali, Bhallataka, Triphala Rasayana</i>
<i>Raktaja(Kunapagandi)</i>	<i>Dhataki pushpa, Aswagandha sadhita hrhita, dadima siddha Grhita</i>
<i>Vatapittaja(ksheena)</i>	<i>Shukrakari kriya</i>
<i>Pittakaphaja(putipuya)</i>	<i>Parushakadi, Vatadi Gana</i>
<i>Vatakaphaja(Grathibhuta)</i>	<i>Palasha Bhasma, Pashana bheda</i>
<i>Mutra purisha Gandhi</i>	<i>Chitraka sadhita Grhita and shodhana Therapy, Hingu and Ushira</i>

General line of treatment for male infertility:

Cause should be evaluated and treated accordingly.

Artava Dusti⁵	Specific Treatment
<i>Vataja</i>	<i>Yoni dhavana with mudgaparni qwatha, Bharangi siddhagrhita, basti</i>
<i>Pittaja</i>	<i>Chandana kalka, Madhuka, Ushira with sugar and milk</i>
<i>Kaphaja</i>	<i>Madanaphala Kalka Yonidharana, Aswagandha Qwatha</i>
<i>Raktaja (Kunapagandi)</i>	<i>Rakthachandana Qwatha orally, Triphala qwatha and kalka for local application</i>
<i>Vatapittaja(ksheena)</i>	<i>Rakthayardhaka kriya</i>
<i>Pittakaphaja(putipuya)</i>	<i>Asadhya</i>
<i>Vatakaphaja(Grathibhuta)</i>	<i>Qwatha of Patha, Gokshura, Trayushana</i>
<i>Sannipatika</i>	<i>Asadhya</i>

- *Apana Vata Anulomana Aushadas*
- *Vrishya and Vajitakarana*
- *Madhura Rasa, Snigdha, Brimhana Aushadas*

Preparations	
<i>Kashaya</i>	<i>Bala+vidari ksheera kashaya, jeevaniya gana ksheera kashaya Sukumari kashaya, vidaryadi kashaya</i>
<i>Arishta/asava</i>	<i>Ashwagandharista, kharjurrasav</i>
<i>Gutika</i>	<i>Manasamitravataka, shilajatwadi vati</i>
<i>Taila</i>	<i>Ashwagandadi yamaka, sukumarendra taila</i>
<i>Ghritha</i>	<i>Ashwagandadi grhitha, amrtaprasha grhitha, phala sarpi</i>
<i>Bhasma</i>	<i>Kukkutanda bhasma, kanta Bhasma</i>
<i>Rasa/dhatu/loha preparations</i>	<i>Pushpadhanwarasa, makara dhwaja rasa</i>

General line of treatment for female infertility

Cause should be evaluated and treated accordingly.

- *Vandhyatva Chikitsa*
- *Atiartava/ Anartava Chikitsa*
- *Garbhashaya Balya Chikitsa*
- *Beejadoshha Chikitsa*
- *Apana Vata Anulomana Chikitsa*
- *Vrishya and Vajikarana Aushadas*
- *Madhura Rasa, Snigdha, Brimhana Aushadas*

Preparations	
<i>Kashaya</i>	<i>Bala+shatavari ksheera kashaya, jeevaniya gana kshegera kashaya Sukumari kashaya, vidaryadi kashaya</i>
<i>Arishta/asava</i>	<i>Ashwagandharista, kharjurrasav, sukumara arista</i>
<i>Gutika</i>	<i>Rajpravartini vati, shilajatwadi vati</i>
<i>Taila</i>	<i>Sukumarendra taila, jeevantiyadi anuvasana taila</i>
<i>Ghritha</i>	<i>Ashwagandadi grhitha, amrtaprasha grhitha, phala sarpi</i>
<i>Bhasma</i>	<i>Kukkutanda bhasma, swarna vanga</i>
<i>Rasa/dhatu/loha preparations</i>	<i>Pushpadhanwarasa, makara dhwaja rasa, nastapushpantaka rasa</i>

Conclusion:

Ayurveda has most unique method and principles of addressing holistic health through *Rasayana* and *Vajikarana* aiding preventive aspect in all ages ranging from neonates to geriatrics. *Ayurveda* focuses on balancing *Tridoshas*, *Agni* and *Saptadhatus*. It bridges gap between *Sharira*, *Atma* and *Mana*. *Rasayana*

modulates neuro-endocrine-immune system. *Rasayana Vajikarana* improves *Shukra* thus improving reproductive health and sexual function. *Vajikarana* also have anti-depressant, anti-anxiety and adaptogenic action to improve mental function. Understanding the cause of infertility will help in diagnosis and accurate treatment. Adapting proper lifestyle and using of *Vajikara* and *Vrishya* formulations will be great boon for people suffering from infertility and societal stigma that comes with it.

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